

Latinx communities have been disproportionately impacted by COVID-19. Higher COVID-19 infection rates among Latinx with limited English proficiency (LEP) are driven by poverty, exclusion from benefits, political disempowerment, and fear of job loss. Latinx immigrants in particular face significant barriers to testing: lack of insurance, language barriers, stigma, work conflicts, and limited transportation. The researchers implemented free community-based testing in partnership with religious leaders and community health workers to ease access and trust issues affecting COVID-19 testing in Latinx communities. High positivity rates in Latinx populations may not have been detected without the implementation of tailored community outreach and low-barrier testing.

WHERE:

Baltimore, Md.

WHEN?

The study took place
June 2020–Oct. 2020

WHO?

57.5% of 1,786 individuals tested were Latinx and **85%** of the Latinxs tested had limited English proficiency (LEP)

THE POPULATION

Latinx participants at these community-based testing sites had limited access to care

92% of patients who tested positive and **82%** of those who tested negative had limited English proficiency

Some Latinxs feared getting testing because of the possibility of losing their job if they tested positive

Many patients tested positive for COVID but didn't have symptoms.

WHAT WORKED: TAILORED INTERVENTIONS

Free community testing events at a trusted site (local church)

Outreach to COVID-19 positive patients by bilingual community health workers (CHWs)

Referral by bilingual CHWs to services which support quarantine (food delivery, hotels, cash assistance, work excuses / return to work letters)

KEY FINDINGS

Community-based testing identified high levels of ongoing SARS-CoV-2 transmission among Latinxs with limited English proficiency (LEP).

Those who tested positive were more likely to be younger, live in larger households, and report Spanish as their preferred language.

Latinxs were almost 10 times more likely to test positive than non-Hispanic Whites.

Immigrant status and English language proficiency are important considerations for researchers studying health disparities. Bilingual, bicultural staff and an easily accessible, trusted site (like the church) helps ease access and trust issues.

Partnerships between researchers and community organizations are critical to ensure testing and support services are accessible, trusted, and responsive to the needs expressed by the community.

This summary was completed in Jan. 2022. This summary includes only results from one single study. Other studies may find different results.

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